

TEACHING TOOLS WITH THE USE OF PROPRIETARY TECHNOLOGIES IN PEDAGOGY CLASSES

Dilbar Negmatovna Alimdjanova

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract: Technology, on the one hand, is associated with a certain system of activities, including certain normative fixed methods of activity, a system of means to ensure its implementation.

Keywords: pedagogical technologies, restructuring of the target, psychological and pedagogical attitudes.

In the modern psychological and pedagogical literature of recent years, the concept of "innovation", "pedagogical technologies", "learning technologies", etc. is quite common. "Technology" as a scientific term originates from the Greek "tehnē" (art, skill skill) and "logos" (science). In the future, the concept of "technology" became quite widely used in other fields of activity, i.e. it acquired a broader interpretation. According to E. de Bono, technology is the process of producing something useful based on the use of knowledge. Currently, the concept of "technology" is used not only in industry, but also in the field of science and education.

On the other hand, the introduction of a new technology leads to a change not only in the activity itself, but also causes a significant restructuring of the target settings, the system of specific knowledge necessary for its implementation. The study and analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature have shown that the concept of "pedagogical technology" has different interpretations for many authors, for example:

Technology is an art, skill, skill, a set of processing methods, state changes.

Learning technology is a chain of actions and operations directed and result-oriented.

Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical attitudes that define a special set and layout of forms, methods, methods, teaching methods, educational tools; it is an organizational and methodological toolkit of the pedagogical process. At the same time, the object of pedagogical technology is understood as the structure and logic of the construction of the pedagogical process, the ways of its organization for the implementation of pedagogical goals in accordance with certain principles and conditions.

Pedagogical technology is a description of the process of achieving the planned learning outcomes. In our understanding, technology is a chain of actions and operations focused on results.

Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human resources and their interaction, which aims to optimize the forms of education.

From the above characteristics, the most significant features and characteristics of pedagogical technologies can be distinguished:

- the technology is developed for a specific pedagogical plan, which is based on a certain methodological, didactic, psychological, philosophical position of the authors or the team of authors;
- the technological chain of its constituent actions, operations and connections is implemented in full compliance with the accepted targets and specific expected results;
- the technology of training provides for the interrelated activities of the teacher and the student, taking into account the possibilities of individualization and differentiation of training, and the use of technical, including computer-based learning tools;
- any training technology is developed and implemented as a solution to a multi-criteria problem with obtaining maximum planned results with a minimum of money and labor spent on it;

- pedagogical technologies are planned taking into account the fact that they can be reproduced by any teacher and will ensure the achievement of the intended results by all students;

- teaching technologies necessarily include various diagnostic (didactic, psychological, sociometric, etc.) procedures containing criteria, indicators and tools for measuring the results of the activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process.

The problem of pedagogical teaching technologies was directly revealed in the works of E.R. Argunov, A.V. Bospalko, V.P. Bospalko, I.V. Borisova, A.S. Verbitsky, A.M. Voronin, V.V. Guzeev, A.E. Denisov, O.V. Dolzhenko, T.A. Ilyina, M.V. Klarin, G.V. Latyshev, T.A. Masharova, E.I. Mashbitsa, G.I. Mikhaylevskaya, V.Y. Pityukova, V.V. Serikova, V.D. Simonenko, I.F. Talyzina, A.I. Uman, O.K. Filatov, A.I. Yakovleva, F. Yanushkevich. In the technological approach to the educational process, the following are distinguished:

- setting goals and their maximum refinement with a focus on achieving results;
- content profiling;
- formulation of materials and organization of the entire course of the educational process in accordance with the educational goals;
- evaluation of current results;
- correction of components of the educational process aimed at achieving goals;
- final evaluation of the results and new goal setting.

The technology of teaching is defined as a set of actions for the selection and determination of the order and sequence of the use of didactic means, the organization of forms and methods of teaching. Learning technology is the process of implementing the learning content that ensures the most effective achievement of the set goals. Classification of learning technologies:

By the object of impact:

- teaching students;
- professional development and retraining of specialists.
- By subject environment:
- for technical disciplines;
- for natural sciences;
- for the humanities;
- for special, artistic disciplines, etc.
- By the means used:
- information;
- video technical;
- problem-activity;
- reflexive , etc .

On the organization of educational material:

- individual;
- collective;
- mixed.

According to the methodical task:

- single-item technology;
- technology of a single tool;
- the technology of one method.

The process of developing a learning technology can be represented as follows:

Creating a learning technology

1. Elements of technology:

- description of pedagogical technologies (methodology and theory);
- the priority of the goal, the ratio to the final result;
- goal specification;
- modeling of the pedagogical process;
- designing the desired result;

- material selection;
- diagnostics and control;
- the system of corrective measures;
- teacher training;
- preparation of students.

2. Organization of educational material:

- selection of the most significant content;
- structuring of educational material;
- selection of examples and proofs taking into account the received specialty;
- definition of educational and creative tasks and tasks aimed at the formation of skills and abilities.

3 Modeling of the pedagogical process (choosing the forms and organization of the educational process or the type of training sessions):

- lectures;
- seminars;
- practical exercises;
- independent work;
- individual work, etc.

The choice of teaching methods:

- information;
- reproductive;
- problem-search;
- reproductive and creative, etc.

Selection of teaching tools and training equipment:

- textbooks and teaching aids;
- visual aids;
- informational materials and audiovisual teaching tools;

- software and methodological support for computers;
- special equipment;
- didactic materials;
- technical means of training, etc.

All this is aimed at competencies that consist of:

To study (aesthetic perception of works of artistic culture (painting, graphics, sculpture, architecture, etc.));

To think (on the creation of work, synthesis of creativity, etc.);

To seek (new ways in solving educational and creative tasks and exercises, etc.);

To create (to get down to business);

Collaborate (during training with a teacher, fellow students, work individually and in a group);

Adapt (to the creative process and the learning process in new conditions).

As a result, we can say that the technology of training consists of four main elements: forms, tools, diagnostics, methods and techniques of training and content.

References

1. Babushkin I.E., Fedorov V.V. Designing work programs of academic disciplines and practices in accordance with the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education: a methodological guide for teachers. – Barnaul: Publishing house of the Altai State Medical University of the Ministry of Health of Russia, 2013. – 92 p.
2. Melnikova I.Yu., Romantsov M.G. Features of medical education and the role of a university teacher in the educational process at the present stage // International Journal of Experimental Education. - 2013. – No. 11. – pp. 47-51.
3. Negmatovna, A. D. (2020). Pedagogical basis of promoting preschool children interest in a healthy lifestyle. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 10, 126-129.

4. Negmatovna, A. D. (2021). The System Of Introduction Of Pedagogical Technologies In The Didactic Processes Of Higher Education On The Example Of Young Psychology. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 3, 12-16.
5. Negmatovna, A. D. (2021). Improving the pedagogical conditions for the introduction of copyright technologies (on the example of the subject of pedagogy). World Bulletin of Social Sciences, 4(11), 17-22.
6. Negmatovna, A. D. (2020). Formation of Ideas About a Healthy Lifestyle in Teaching Children of Senior Preschool Age. psychologist, 7(5).
7. Negmatovna, ALIMDJANOVA Dilbar, and AZMIEVA Elzara Ernestovna. "Use of Modern Digital Technologies in the Education System." ECLSS Online 2020a (2020): 181.
8. ALIMDJANOVA, D. N., & BERDIEV, D. V. (2022). THEORETICAL METHODOLOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS IMPROVING PEDAGOGICAL TERMS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF AUTHOR TECHNOLOGIES. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (2), 201-205.